

A STUDY ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL BRAIDS

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SUMMARY: This paper describes a study of the microstructure of three-dimensional braids produced by a four-step method. An analytical approach is employed in conjunction with experimental investigations to establish the relationship between the braid structure and braiding parameters. Based on microscopic observations of yarn orientation and distortion, we divide a three-dimensional braid structure into three representative regions, i.e., the interior, surface and corner, and establish three types of microstructural unit-cell models for the three regions, respectively. An equivalent cross sectional area has been defined by averaging the effect of yarn localised distortion, based on which, the yarn packing factor has been examined at the jamming conditions. Expressions for the fibre volume fractions in the three regions and the whole braided composite have been derived accordingly. Based on these expressions, the total fibre volume fractions in several braided composites have been calculated and found to be in good agreement with experimental results.

KEYWORDS: three-dimensional braids, microstructure, braided composites

INTRODUCTION

The properties and performance of a three-dimensional braided composite depend primarily on the microstructure of braided preform and the mechanical and physical properties of the constituent materials. In the past, a considerable amount of effort has been placed on the understanding of the microstructure of braids. Ko [1] first identified a unit cell representing the fiber architecture of rectangular braided preforms, which was a cuboid containing four diagonally intersecting yarns. Later Du and Ko [2] re-examined the earlier treatment and found that the unit cell was oversimplified and incorrect. Li et al [3] reported an experimental study of the internal structure of braids and identified a unit cell for braided composites, based on the assumptions that yarns were straight rods with a circular cross-section and there were no lateral deformations at the yarn cross-over points. Li et al also observed that the structure on the surface of the braid preforms was different from that in the interior. Subsequent studies conducted by Lei [4] and Kosher [5] revealed that the corners were unique in the preform structure. Recently, Wang [6] presented an analysis of the topological structure in three-dimensional braided preforms and defined three distinctive types of unit cells in the preform interior, surface and corner regions, respectively.

To date, the topological structure of three-dimensional braids, which is determined by the braiding sequence and number of yarns, can generally be understood on the basis of previous models. However, experimental evidence [7] showed that the mechanical performance of 3D braided composites deteriorated greatly by cutting the edge off the preform. Moreover, the mechanical properties of the braided composites were affected by the

yarn bundle size. These phenomena cannot be explained by existing models. Therefore, there is a need to use more realistic geometrical unit cells, which combine the braid topology with the yarn configuration, in order to successfully predict the mechanical properties of the three-dimensional braided composites. This paper presents a study of the microstructure of three-dimensional braids fabricated by a four-step method. An analytical approach is employed in conjunction with experimental investigations to establish the relationship between the braid structure and the braiding parameters.

MICROSCOPIC OBSERVATIONS

Eight samples of three dimensional braid preforms were made by the four-step method. The specifications for the braids are given in Table 1. Carbon fibre T300-12K, an epoxy resin TED-85 and a curing agent, acid anhydride-70, were used to fabricate the composite samples. The curing conditions were: 130°C for 2 hours, then 150°C for 1 hour, followed by 160°C for 8 hours and finally 180°C for 3 hours. The final dimensions of the composite samples were 250 x 25 x 6 (mm³). Samples of the braid preforms were embedded in a resin, Nej-o-lac, such that the cutting of the braids became easy and the yarns could be carefully removed from the braids without alternating their original shapes. The rectangular braids were cut at 45° to its sides. Optical and electron scanning microscopes were used to examine the yarn surface and the interior of braid preforms.

Table 1: Specifications of samples

Samples	D _y (mm)	m × n	α	h(mm)	γ	θ	β
HKT3002-1	0.757	22 × 6	19.0	5.22	26.0	10.8	7.3
HKT3003-1	0.757	22 × 6	21.0	4.70	28.5	12.0	8.1
HKT3004-1	0.757	22 × 6	21.0	4.73	28.5	12.0	8.1
HKT3005-1	0.757	22 × 6	21.5	4.60	29.1	12.3	8.3
HKT3002-2	0.757	19 × 5	40.0	2.57	49.9	25.0	17.3
HKT3003-2	0.757	19 × 5	40.0	2.59	49.9	25.0	17.3
HKT3004-2	0.757	19 × 5	40.0	2.60	49.9	25.0	17.3
HKT3005-2	0.757	19 × 5	39.0	2.64	48.9	24,2	16.7

Fig. 1: SEM micrograph of the interior of a four-step braid interior

Figure 1 is a micrograph of the cross-section in the braiding interior cut at a 45° angle with the braid surface. It shows that the axes of the multifilament yarns remain straight in spite of

having lateral deformation at the yarn surface. Moreover, there is an additional yarn tortuosity caused by the braiding process and this tortuosity changes direction according to the braider movement. Microscopic evidence further reveals that large localized distortions of the yarn occur along the yarn, as shown by the configuration of the yarn drawn from the braid interior in Figure 2. This indicates that the helical traces have been formed on the yarn surface and the fibers are no longer parallel to the yarn axes due to the lateral compression of adjacent yarns.

BASIC ASSUMPTIONS

In our analysis of the geometrical structure of a braid, the following assumptions have been made:

1. The cross-section of the multifilament braiding yarns is elliptical with major and minor radii, a and b , respectively;
2. In all the three regions, the braiding yarns have a uniform cross sectional area; thus a uniform packing factor is assumed along the length after jamming;
3. The braiding process is quite stable so that the braid structure is uniform, at least over a certain length;
4. All yarns in the braid structure have the same size and flexibility.

Fig. 2: SEM micrograph of a braiding yarn in braid interior

Fig. 3: Schematic illustration of the interior, surface and corner of a braid

In the braid interior, every yarn is subjected to lateral compression of six adjacent yarns with different directions. In our present analysis, an equivalent area of yarn cross section is defined as the average of yarn cross sectional area along the length in a unit cell. Let Ω represents the area of the cross-section of the elliptical yarns, and $s(l)$ the area of the cross-section of the distorted yarn along the yarn length, then, $\bar{\Omega}$ is defined as:

$$\Omega = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L s(l) dl \tag{1}$$

where L is the length of a yarn in a unit-cell.

THREE TYPES OF UNIT CELLS

Selection of Control Volumes

As shown in Figure 3, a braid has a skin-core structure and can be divided into three regions: interior, surface and corner regions. Each of these three regions is built up by an identical unit cell, respectively, though the exact manner of composition depends on the initial yarn carrier pattern. The traces of yarn carriers in the interior, on the surface and the corner have their unique features, which lead to the different yarn structures in the three regions. These regions must be treated separately.

Fig. 4: The movement of carriers during a machine cycle [6×6:(1-1)]

Although the braiding process is achieved by translational permutations of column and row tracks, these permutations can be combined into a rotational operation as indicated by the diagonal lines in Figures 4b and 4c. Considering the carrier positions after every 2 and 4 steps, the carriers connected by these lines exchange their positions by rotation. These continuous rotational exchanges result in the repeatability of the topological structure in the braid interior. In our analysis, a control volume method is employed to describe the topological structure of a three-dimensional braid. The control volume for the interior is defined by the cuboid enclosed by carriers 33, 34, 45, 55, 64, 63, 52 and 42 in the original pattern and two parallel planes separated by the height of four braiding steps. There are twelve yarns in this control volume. The control volume for the surface is represented by a cylinder with the bottom area enclosed by carriers 64, 65 and 74 while the corner one is enclosed by carriers 66 and 76.

Fig. 5: Yarn paths in braid interior during four braiding steps

Braid Interior Region

In the interior control volume, carriers 34, 55, 63 and 42 remain in the control volume after the 4-step machine cycle while the others move out. The spatial traces of the yarn carried by carriers 34, 43 and 61 during the four braiding steps are shown in Figure 5a, where the lines connecting the yarn carriers represent the yarn axes. Note that carriers 34, 43 exchange their respective positions after step 2 and carriers 34, 61 do so after step 4. Thus the yarn follows a zigzag trace before compacting. However, when a uniform yarn-compacting action is applied by yarn jamming, the yarns will be straightened and repositioned in the space as shown in Figure 5b. Figures 5b-5e illustrate the configuration of the axes of all the twelve yarns in the four sections of the control volume. Assembling the four sections, the unit-cell of the braid interior can be obtained as shown in Figure 6a.

Fig. 6: A unit-cell (a), a quarter unit-cell (b) and two sub-cells (c and d) in the braid interior

According to the orientation angles, the braid interior comprises four groups of yarns, and intersecting two sets of parallel planes of a cuboid. The control volume can be further divided

into eight sub-cuboids as shown in Figure 6. Among the eight sub-cuboids, there are only two non-identical sub-cuboids which can be re-assembled into the control volume in an alternating manner. The axes of the twelve yarns inside the control volume or unit cell are all straight and do not intersect each other in the space. The distance between the two yarn axes in a sub-cell is $2b$ where b is the minor radius of the yarn.

Braid Surface Region

As shown in Figure 4a, the control volume for the braid surface is defined by the cylinder with a bottom area including carriers 64, 65 and 74 in the original pattern and two parallel planes with a separation equal to the height of four braiding steps. The yarn carrier movements in the control volume are shown in Figure 7a. As an example, let us follow the movement of carrier 64: it enters the surface control volume from the interior at step 0, moves one position along $+X$ -direction at step 1, and then shifts one position along $-Y$ -direction at step 2, holds its position at step 3, moves one position along $+Y$ -direction at step 4, then leaves the control volume and returns to the interior. Similar movements also occur for carriers 74 and 56. After jamming, the yarns will be repositioned, as shown in Figure 7b.

Fig. 7: The yarn trace and the unit-cell on the braid surface

The yarn axes are spatial curves comprising a straight line and a segment of a helix, not just straight lines. For these two distinct segments, different orientation angles are required. In a surface unit-cell, there are three yarns divided into two groups.

Braid Corner Region

At the corners of a braid, a control volume is defined by the cylinder with bottom area including carriers 66 and 76 (as shown in Figure 4a) and two parallel planes separated by the length of four braiding steps. For instance, carrier 66 comes into the control volume at step 0 from the interior, shifts its position from step 1 to step 6 according to the braiding process and re-enters the interior at step 7. Upon yarn jamming, the yarns adjust to the positions shown in Figure 8b, where the helical yarn is inclined to the braid axis by the corner braiding angle β . Thus, as shown in Figures 8c and 8d, a unit-cell at the braid corner can be defined, such that it has a height of h and two helical yarns do not intersect each other's axis.

Fig. 8: Yarn traces at the corner and the corner unit-cell : (a) Yarn traces during 8 steps of braiding; (b) Yarn traces after jamming; (c) and (d) The unit cell for the corner region.
 Relationship Between the Three Regions

Suppose one carrier in the interior occupies one unit volume. For a $m \times n$ braid, the volumes of the regions in term of the unit volume, as can be seen from Figures 9, are given in Table 2:

Table 2: Volumes occupied by the interior, surface and corner regions

Units	M and N are Even Numbers	M or N is not an Even Number
Surface	$3(m + n - 4) / 2$	$3(m + n - 2) / 2$
Corner	4	2
Interior	$mn - m - n + 2$	$mn - m - n + 1$
Total	$mn + (m + n) / 2$	$mn + (m + n) / 2$

Fig. 9: Volume occupied by the interior, surface and corner regions

Thus for the braids with m and n both even, the volume proportions of the regions in the whole structure can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i &= \frac{2(m-1)(n-1)+2}{2mn+m+n} \\
 V_s &= \frac{3(m+n-4)}{2mn+m+n} \\
 V_c &= \frac{8}{2mn+m+n}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Similarly, for the case where either m or n is an odd number , the volume proportions of the regions are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i &= \frac{2(m-1)(n-1)}{2mn+m+n} \\
 V_s &= \frac{3(m+n-2)}{2mn+m+n} \\
 V_c &= \frac{4}{2mn+m+n}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

YARN PACKING FACTOR

The yarn packing factor can be defined as:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\pi D_y^2}{4\Omega} = \frac{D_y^2}{4ab} \tag{4}$$

where D_y is the equivalent diameter of a solid braiding yarn, which is determined by the yarn tex and fibre density.

From the triangle marked in Figure 11b, we have the following geometric relation:

$$h = 8b / \tan \gamma \tag{5}$$

Fig. 10: The geometry of the jamming condition

Upon yarn jamming, the yarns contact each other as shown in Figure 10. The equations for the inclined elliptical-cylinder surface of two braiding yarns, Y1 and Y2, in the given coordinate system are:

$$Y1: [(x - 8b) \cos \gamma + z \sin \gamma]^2 / a^2 + (y - 3b)^2 / b^2 = 1 \quad (6)$$

$$Y2: (x - 3b)^2 / b^2 + [(y - 4b) \cos \gamma + z \sin \gamma]^2 / a^2 = 1 \quad (7)$$

The plane, S, which is parallel to the elliptical-cylinders, Y1 and Y2, can be described by the following expression:

$$Ax + By + Cz + D = 0 \quad (8)$$

The orientation vector of the axis of the elliptical-cylinder Y1 is $\{-\sin \gamma, 0, \cos \gamma\}$. The plane S is parallel to Y1, thus the following condition is satisfied:

$$A = C / \tan \gamma \quad (9)$$

The orientation vector of the axis of the elliptical-cylinder Y2 is $\{0, -\sin \gamma, \cos \gamma\}$. The plane S is parallel to Y2; similarly, we have:

$$B = C / \tan \gamma \quad (10)$$

Dividing Equation 8 by $C/\tan \gamma$ yields :

$$x + y + z \tan \gamma + D' = 0 \quad (11)$$

Since the plane S is a tangent plane to Y1 defined by Equation 6, then, by letting $x=4b$, and solving Equations 6 and 11, there must be one and only one real solution:

$$D' = -11b + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 \cos^2 \gamma} / \cos \gamma \quad (12)$$

A similar relation exists for Y2. Plane S is a tangent plane to Y2 described by Equation 7. Letting $y=4b$ and solving Equations 7 and 11 leads to

$$D' = -7b - \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 \cos^2 \gamma} / \cos \gamma \quad (13)$$

By equating Equations 12 and 13, we obtain:

$$a = b\sqrt{3} \cos \gamma \quad (14)$$

Substituting Equations 5 and 14 into Equation 4, the expression for the yarn-packing factor ϵ can be rewritten as follows:

$$\epsilon = 16\sqrt{3}D_y^2 / (3h^2 \tan^2 \gamma \cos \gamma) = 16\sqrt{3} / (3h_d^2 \tan^2 \gamma \cos \gamma) \quad (15)$$

where $h_d = h/D_y$, is a normalized pitch length.

FIBRE VOLUME FRACTION

With reference to Figure 6, the fiber volume fraction in the braid interior can then be obtained by multiplying the yarn volume fraction by the yarn-packing factor.

$$V_{if} = \frac{Y_i}{U_i} \varepsilon = \frac{2\pi}{h_d^2 \tan^2 \gamma \cos \gamma} \quad (16)$$

From Figure 7, the fiber volume fraction in a braid surface can be estimated as:

$$V_{sf} = \frac{Y_s}{U_s} \varepsilon = \frac{4\pi}{3h_d^2 \tan^2 \gamma} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{4} \tan^2 \gamma} + \frac{1}{\cos \theta} \right) \quad (17)$$

From Figure 8, the fiber volume fraction at a braid corner can be given as:

$$V_{cf} = \frac{Y_c}{U_c} \varepsilon = \frac{3\pi}{h_d^2 \tan^2 \gamma \cos \beta} \quad (18)$$

Finally, the total fiber volume fraction in a braid can be written as:

$$V_f = V_i V_{if} + V_s V_{sf} + V_c V_{cf} \quad (19)$$

Table 3 lists the calculated and experimental values of fibre volume fraction of several braid composites. Good agreement between the theoretical predictions (TV_f) and experimental data (EV_f) of the total fibre volume fraction has been obtained. The calculated values also indicate that the fibre volume fractions on the surface (TV_s) and at the corners (TV_c) are higher than that in interior (TV_i) when the braiding angle is small (20°). However this trend reverses when the braiding angle is larger (40°).

Table 3: Comparison between the theoretical and experimental values of fibre volume fraction

Samples	EV _f (%)	TV _f (%)	TV _i (%)	TV _s (%)	TV _c (%)	V _i	V _s	V _c	ε(%)
HKT3002-1	65.42	66.06	61.98	76.06	84.27	0.726	0.247	0.027	91.13
HKT3003-1	68.70	66.70	62.93	75.91	83.80	0.726	0.247	0.027	92.52
HKT3004-1	68.33	65.86	62.14	74.95	82.74	0.726	0.247	0.027	91.35
HKT3005-1	69.07	66.43	62.77	75.36	83.12	0.726	0.247	0.027	92.28
HKT3002-2	61.09	59.59	60.07	58.48	60.81	0.673	0.308	0.019	88.32
HKT3003-2	60.35	58.68	59.15	57.58	59.87	0.673	0.308	0.019	86.96
HKT3004-2	59.97	58.23	58.70	57.14	59.41	0.673	0.308	0.019	86.30
HKT3005-2	61.18	59.66	59.89	59.05	61.68	0.673	0.308	0.019	88.05

CONCLUSION

In this paper, an analysis of the microstructure of three-dimensional braids produced by a four-step method has been presented. Three distinct unit cells have been defined for the three regions of a 4-step braid made from multifilament yarns. According to the yarn orientation angles, the braid interior has been represented by a unit cell comprising twelve straight yarns, intersecting two sets of parallel planes of the cuboid unit cell which can be further divided into eight sub-cells. Among the eight sub-cells, there are only two non-identical cells which can be re-assembled into the unit cell in an alternating manner. In the surface unit cell, the braiding yarn axes are spatial curves comprising a straight line and a segment of a helix. For these two distinct segments, different orientation angles have been determined. The unit-cell at the braid corner has been defined, as having two helical yarns which do not intersect each other's axis.

In addition, an equivalent cross sectional area was defined by averaging the effect of yarn localized distortion, based on which, the yarn packing factor has been examined at the jamming conditions. Expressions for the fibre volume fractions in the three regions and the whole braided composite have been derived accordingly. Based on these expressions, the total fiber volume fraction in several braided composites have been calculated and found to be in good agreement with experimental results.

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REFERENCES

1. Ko,F.K., "Three dimensional fabrics for composites-an introduction to the magnawave structure", *Proc. ICCM-4, Japan Soc. Composite Material*, Tokyo, Japan, 1982, p.1609.
2. Du,G.W. & Ko,F.K., "Unit cell geometry of 3-D braided structure", *Proc.Am. Soc.Com.*, 1991.
3. W.Li, M.Hammad and A.El-Shiekh, "Structural analysis of 3-D braided preforms for composites", *J. Text. Inst.*, 1990, 81 No 40, p.491-514.
4. Lei,C., Cai,Y.j. & Ko,F.K., "Finite element analysis of 3-D braided composite", *In Adv. in Eng.Software and Workstations*, Elsevier Science, 1992, p.187-194.
5. T.D.Kostar and T-W.Chou, "Design and automated fabrication of 3-D braided preforms for advanced structural composites", *Computer Aided Design in Composite Material Technology III*, Elsevier Science, 1992, p.63-78.
6. Y.Q.Wang & A.S.D.Wang, "On the topological yarn structure of 3-D rectangular and tubular braided preforms", *Composites Science and Technology*, 51(1994), p.575-586.
7. F.K Ko, "Three Dimensional fabrics for composites", in "*Textile Structural Composites*", Elsevier, 1989.